

R1 – Concept Paper for a Pedagogical Framework.

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Table 1: Deliverable Factsheet

Consortium

	Name	Short Name	Country
1	Aalborg University	AAU	Denmark
2	Tallinn University of Technology	TALTECH	Estonia
3	University of Limerick	UL	Ireland

Table 2: Consortium

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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations	Description
DLTs	Distributed Ledger Technologies
PBL	Problem-Based Learning

OERs	Open Educational Resources
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
DBL	Design Based Learning

Table 4: List of Abbreviations

Authors

Report written by Andy Peruccon, Dr. Luca Simeone and Dr Roisin Lyons with the contribution from the wider BC4ECO consortium team.

1. Overview

The purpose of this paper is to present a learning pedagogy as part of the first result of the BC4ECO project, whose goal is to assist professionals in Computer science, Design and Environmental Engineering in utilising Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), and to devise new and decentralised approaches for addressing Environmental Sustainability concerns. Contextualising DLTs within environmental sustainability paves the way for many paradigm shifts within theories of learning and towards novel epistemological and methodological concerns. When looking at the applications of DLTs for environmental purposes, we find the work of many authors who pointed at the possibility to utilise blockchain (as part of DLTs) within carbon trading (Muzumdar et al., 2022), waste management (França et al., 2020), trust in sustainable supply chains (Bai et al., 2022), transparency and trust in environmental monitoring and reporting as well as tracking and managing carbon offset markets (Parmentola et al., 2022). Not only are DLTs relevant to the topic of sustainable innovation, but as argued by Parmentola et al. (2022), innovative application of blockchain technology within governments and industries can create systems of incentives that can induce environmentally friendly behaviours (ibid.). The shift of focus from more traditional applications of DLTs (historically more applied to the field of economy and finance) leads to innovative ways to engage with different types of systems requiring various sorts of capabilities.

European Higher Education Institutions already address the need to develop novel infrastructures dealing with the practical aspect of DLTs in economic and governmental systems. Nevertheless, there are emerging requirements that make us consider the importance of the design of systems and networks of stakeholders that strongly contribute to the creation of value within decentralised systems (Upadhyay et al., 2021). In order to fully harness the potential of DLTs to address environmental challenges, it is necessary to go beyond subject-specific learning and consider broader non-technical issues (Hindes & Bakker, 2004), and to learn about the entire system where challenges and

solutions are situated. This is highly required in contemporary workplaces (ibid.) while many European universities still fall short in teaching DLTs with the non-technical skills required to address environmental problems. The wicked and multifaceted nature of environmental challenges, as already noted in the past by Rittel and Webber (1973), calls for novel ways to engage with and deal with them. Technological innovation is the result of the interplay of a complex network of actors, including scientists, designers, and even objects and machines (Latour, 1987; Boeler & Kaethler, 2020). Therefore, within this context, the goal of the BC4ECO project is to advance novel ways of looking at technological innovation, where paradigm shifts are satisfied in both the way learners engage with problems as well as the way in which they interpret the necessary information to address them.

One of the initial results envisioned by BC4ECO is a pedagogical framework, which informs all the subsequent research and development activities. This concept paper comprises an exhaustive description of the pedagogical framework and the underlying learning pedagogy. The document presents the incorporating philosophical underpinnings, target groups, motivations, principles for learning and methods for evaluation related to this pedagogical framework. Taking the example of non-functional features of DLTs, the learning pedagogies identified both a decentralised and critical mindset that is necessary for learners. One example is demonstrated in the role of a decentralised framework for learning, where platforms such as Open Educational Resources (OERs) enable the distribution of educational material online for use and repurposing. The decentralised nature of the pedagogy advances distributed learning and promotes cross-collaboration within open boundaries where teachers and learners worldwide engage in innovative and networked ways of addressing environmental wicked problems. Our distributed pedagogy stems from Problem-Based Learning (PBL), a pedagogical approach that promotes student-centred learning by tackling real-world problems through open-ended and critical problem formulation in a collaborative setting (Barrows & Tamblyn, 1980; Savin-Baden, 2014). It aims to foster a shift in mindset towards decentralisation and environmental sustainability by encouraging students to engage with complex and systemic issues and to think critically and creatively about possible solutions.

The Pedagogical Framework has been visualised and summarised in a Miro board (see Figure1), which is open for access.

Figure 1: The 'Framework on a page', which follows the initial structure of the learning pedagogy comprising of (1) a vision, (2) Theoretical & Curricular underpinnings, (3) Principles for teaching and learning, (4) key teaching practices and (5) Pedagogical Evaluation. The model is available by following this link: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPzfwzbs/>

The core components of the pedagogical framework are:

- **Vision:** where the core strategic orientation of BC4ECO is formulated as the need to inspire and support learners to succeed as creative, critical and environmentally conscious thinkers.
- **Learning model:** where the goals and the target audience of BC4ECO are specified, also in relation to PBL as the core pedagogical model: an inquiry-based and student-centred instructional approach that emphasizes critical thinking, problem-solving and the application of knowledge to real-world challenges. This model is developed to integrate further processes connected to critical thinking, behavioural change and design-based learning.

- **Principles for teaching and learning:** where some core principles from the above-mentioned learning model are distilled (e.g., Critical Reflection, Self-directed learning, Group work and P2P collaboration)
- **Key teaching practices:** where the primary teaching practices connected to our chosen learning model are presented (e.g., Flipped Classroom, Designerly and Systemic approaches to problems, Review of multiple sources)
- **Pedagogical evaluation:** where we highlight methods to assess the quality and effectiveness of the educational practices carried out within BC4ECO and connected to its learning model.

1.1 BC4ECO Consortium

Aalborg University (AAU)

At Aalborg University, all educational activities are centred around Problem-Based project work, which is based on a set of principles known as the Aalborg Model of Problem-Based Learning (PBL). This approach - which is integrated into all curricula at the university, has gained recognition internationally and has attracted a lot of interest from universities, researchers, and students both in Denmark and abroad. The Aalborg Model emphasises authentic problem-solving through self-directed group work and collaboration. It provides students with the skills to independently gain knowledge, develop competencies, and work with external partners to solve real-world problems.

AAU Team

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Table 5: AAU Team

University of Limerick

Established in 1972, the University of Limerick is an independent, internationally focused university with over 17,500 students and approximately 1,800 staff. It is a young, energetic and enterprising university with a proud record of innovation in education and excellence in research and scholarship. The University of Limerick has been awarded a 5-star rating from the globally recognised QS Stars rating system (2023), placing UL in the top 2% of all universities worldwide. UL's Kemmy Business School is now placed in the top 1% of business schools worldwide, having recently secured the “triple crown” of accreditation (EQUIS, AACSB and AMBA).

UL Team

Name: Prof. Tiziana Margaria

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	<p>Name: Dr. Roisin Lyons</p> <p>Title: Lecturer of Innovation and Entrepreneurship</p>
	<p>Name: Ahmad Chaudhary</p> <p>Title: Technical Officer, PhD student, professional services consultant.</p>

Table 6: UL Team

TALTECH

Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech) is the only flagship in engineering and IT science and education in Estonia, providing higher education at all levels in engineering and technology, information technology, economics, science, and maritime. TalTech's mission is to be a promoter of science, technology, and innovation and a leading provider of engineering and economic education in Estonia.

TALTECH team

A portrait photograph of Istemi Demirag, a man with short grey hair, wearing a dark suit jacket over a patterned shirt.	<p>Name: Istemi Demirag Title: Professor in Accounting</p>
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	<p>Name: Viktoria Voronova</p> <p>Title: Senior lecturer in environmental engineering and management</p>
	<p>Name: Sadok Ben Yahia</p> <p>Title: Full Professor at the Technology University of Tallinn (TalTech)</p>

Table 7: TALTECH Team

2. Theoretical and pedagogical underpinnings

Increasingly, scholars and practitioners have been interested in how an intensive use of design frameworks, methods and approaches can support learning (Lynch et al., 2019; Mehalik & Schunn, 2006) and teaching processes (Schön, 1987). These techniques are particularly useful for addressing social issues because it allows people to think outside the box and develop innovative ideas, by viewing the problem from multiple perspectives with empathy (Brown, 2008) and a user-centric approach to solution-making. This process is especially important for social and sustainable innovation concepts, in which it is essential to know the context, understand the elements of a problem, and experiment with possible and iterative solutions (Brown & Wyatt, 2010).

For the purposes of this project, the principles of design-based learning will be the lens through which the pedagogical elements will be designed. A marriage between design thinking methodologies

and problem-based learning, this typology is an optimum fit for the design of our programme. As such it is imperative that the theories from which design-based learning emanates from be outlined, considering elements of constructivism, problem-based learning, and design based learning. Secondly, the development of a robust pedagogical framework must consider both the student, the content, and the context. As such, we will explore a number of key areas which will help to shape the conceptual framework, noting the intention to teach students using hybrid approaches, and the biases which may affect the student during the experiential learning process.

2.1 Theoretical considerations

2.1.1 Constructivism

Constructivism is an approach to teaching and learning that places the students at the centre of their educational process (Ertmer and Newby, 1993). According to this theory, learners construct their own knowledge by actively engaging with their environment, making sense of it, and “creating meaning from their own experiences” (ibid, p.55). The context in which learning occurs is crucial in constructivist pedagogies, as learners create meaningful concepts and validate them in the real world (Kalamas Hedden et al., 2017). When looking at the topic of sustainability, Kalamas Hedden et al. (2017), highlight how teaching students to solve real challenges prepares them for sustainability-related issues. The complexity of sustainability challenges requires students to fully immerse in experiential learning processes, where they can explore, discover and understand how to identify problems and critically evaluate potential solutions. Experiential learning – a constructivist learning theory defined as 'learning by doing', positions the learner as an active participant in the educational process. Rather than perceiving learners as recipients of information through frontal lectures (Hawkins, 2000), constructive and experiential learning is achieved through a continuous cycle of inquiry, reflection, analysis and synthesis (Bartle, 2015). Considering relevant theories situated in the educational sciences, **the experiential learning theory**, as described by Kolb (1984), involves a 2-axis model that displays learning styles through exploration, research, testing, and reflection created by Beckman and Barry (2007). The two methods for processing information are (i) learning from concrete experience and ii) via abstract conceptualization of ideas or *abstraction*. The remaining two aspects note the methods of processing of experience which range from reflective observation to active experimentation (Beckman & Barry, 2007; Kolb, 1984). It is considered that his model may prove to be a useful tool to show the various aspects of ‘Blockchain for Sustainability’ that are more concrete and observable balanced with the more abstract and theoretical. By engaging in a learning mode that moves mindfully through these axes a greater functional understanding of the concept can be achieved. Surely, this type of approach also found many applications within e-learning and remote learning as a way to empower a pedagogical philosophy centred on the student’s needs (Keengwe et al., 2014). Many pedagogies emerge from a constructivist approach to learning, and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is one of them.

2.1.2 Problem based learning

Constellations of Problem-Based Learning					
	<i>Constellation 1: Problem-Based Learning for Knowledge Management</i>	<i>Constellation 2: Problem-Based Learning Through Activity</i>	<i>Constellation 3: Project-Led Problem-Based Learning</i>	<i>Constellation 4: Problem-Based Learning for Practical Capabilities</i>	<i>Constellation 5: Problem-Based Learning for Design Based Learning</i>
Problem Type	Designed to promote cognitive competence	Designed to promote learning through activity	Project-led	Practical resolution	Design-based
Level of Interaction	Problem-focused	Activity-focused	Project team	Practical action	Activity-focused
Focus of Knowledge	Mode 1: Propositional knowledge that is produced within academe separate from its use	Mode 2: Knowledge that transcends disciplines and is produced in, and validated through, the world of work	Mode 2: Knowledge that transcends disciplines and is produced in, and validated through, the world of work.	Mode 2: Knowledge that transcends disciplines and is produced in, and validated through, the world of work.	Mode 2: Knowledge that transcends disciplines and is produced in, and validated through, the world of work.
Form of Facilitation	Directive	Activity-focused	Project management	Guide to practice	Project management
Focus of Assessment	Testing of knowledge	Competence for the world of work	Project management	Competence for the world of work	Design critique and professional capabilities
Learning Emphasis	Knowledge management	Development of capabilities	Completion of project	Development of capabilities	Development of design-based capabilities

Table 8: A representation of different constellations of problem-based learning approaches (Savin-Baden, 2014)

PBL, or Problem-Based Learning is an educational approach where students learn by actively engaging with real -world problem and challenges. It is a student-centered and collaborative approach that emphasizes critical thinking, problem-solving and self-directed learning (Leary et al., 2019). This approach is centred around the idea that students learn best when they apply theoretical and research-based knowledge to practical problems. The model also helps students develop their communication and collaboration skills, and provides them with the tools to take an analytical and results-driven approach to problem-solving. PBL has been popularized in the 1980s (Barrows & Tamblyn, 1980; Boud, 1985; Walton & Matthews, 1989) and has since developed in a variety of applications that put an emphasis on different aspects, from those PBL activities specifically oriented to developing practical capabilities, up to the collaborative distributed PBL, all the way up to the use of PBL for transformation and social reform (Savin-Baden, 2014). All these applications tend to share a common understanding of PBL as an interdisciplinary activity- and group-based learning in which students (a) explore a complex, real world problem situation, (b) examine potential gaps in their knowledge and skills and (c) assess what information they need to acquire through self-directed learning to address the problem (de Graaf & Kolmos, 2003; Savin-Baden & Major, 2004). In the table reported below, Savin-Baden more closely looks at some of the features of problem-based learning, e.g. the level of interaction is activity-focused, the

form of facilitation is close to project management, the learning emphasis is on the development of design-based capabilities and the focus of assessment is based on the format of design critique.

While reviewing a variety of applications of PBL, Maggi Savin-Baden introduces the notion of “design-based learning” (Savin-Baden, 2014). Like other applications of PBL, design-based learning is an interdisciplinary and group-based learning activity in which students explore a complex, real world problem situation, examine potential gaps in their knowledge and skills and assess what information they need to acquire through self-directed learning to address the problem (de Graaf & Kolmos, 2003; Savin-Baden & Major, 2004). However, the specific aspect of design-based learning is that it is particularly geared to engage students in activities such as the creation of artefacts, products or services at various stages of development. In this form of PBL, it is important that the design problem is realistic “so that the capabilities students learn will be transferable to the world of work; thus, the learning process in this constellation is seen as being one that strongly mirrors professional practice” (Savin-Baden, 2014, p. 206).

2.1.3 Design Based Learning

Design-based learning has been characterised as a specific process in which learning occurs by directly engaging with complex problems and trying to apply solutions to real-life settings and making intensive use of hands-on design frameworks, methods, and approaches (Mehalik & Schunn, 2006) in collaborative environments (Chen & Chiu, 2016). The learning process is strictly anchored to the very act of designing or, as suggested by Schön, to design moves, wherein the designers try out certain options by creating a sketch, a model, or a prototype, by sharing these artefacts with other stakeholders to get their feedback and then by reflecting upon these moves (Schön, 1987).

Figure 2: Learning styles within the stages of an innovation process (Beckman and Barry, 2007)

Beckman and Barry proposed a matrix (Figure 2) in which they plotted an innovation process as linked to the four different learning styles of Kolb (noted in section 2.1.2.) – diverging, assimilating, converging and accommodating (Kolb, 1984/2014) – and four stages: (1) observation as a deep understanding of the customers and the context of engagement, (2) the development of frameworks to frame data, extract patterns and identify insights, (3) the definition of imperatives or requirements of the ideas to be developed and, finally, (4) the generation of solutions and user/customer experiences that can be tested (Beckman & Barry, 2007). The authors specify that the “the path need not follow the steps in the order in which we described them, nor does it have to spend an equal amount of time in each quadrant. It may, for example, go from observation to frameworks to solutions and back to frameworks again in an attempt to elicit enough information to form meaningful imperatives” (Beckman & Barry, 2007, p. 50). Beckman and Barry argued that design approaches and methods are particularly suitable to support exploratory – rather than purely linear - moves across the quadrants and, consequently, to support innovation-oriented learning processes. Based on a survey of teachers and students who experienced DBL and an analysis of related teaching materials, Gomez et al. (2012) noted that there exist a number of inconsistencies within the taught curriculum of DBL in their sample of engineering

courses. They highlight a number of key characteristics of DBL pertaining to project features in Table 9.

Project feature	Examples
<p>Open-ended</p>	<p>No unique solution is given</p> <p>Search alternatives and solutions</p> <p>Students define the problem, the goals, and the specifications</p> <p>No specification is given. Students are requested to determine own procedures and testing plan</p> <p>Incomplete information is provided at the start. Process of consultation and questioning help to arrive to a fully developed specification</p> <p>Freedom in task implementation to encourage diversity in design approaches</p> <p>Project proposal based on project planning and implementation</p> <p>Case reasoning approach to solve problems</p> <p>Design methodology involved in set up of project activities</p>
<p>Hands-on experiences/experiential</p>	<p>Students apply theory in practical schemes</p> <p>Students conduct experiments and learn from iterations</p> <p>Design methodology embedded in projects</p> <p>Encouraging reflection based on experiencing</p>

<p>Authentic/real-life scenarios</p>	<p>Realistic scenarios: assignments represent real-life engineering problems; teacher/tutor represent customer's role</p> <p>Students are put in scenarios as company workers in design projects</p> <p>Linking project activities to industry: company is issuer of assignment; provides feedback</p>
<p>Multidisciplinary</p>	<p>Integration of content from different disciplines</p> <p>Teachers/expertise from different disciplines involve in project</p>

Table 9: Characteristics of DBL pertaining to project features (Gomez Puente et al., 2012)

2.2 Pedagogical Considerations

To develop a robust conceptual framework for the BC4ECO project, a number of pedagogical elements need to be considered. Pedagogical Content Knowledge or PCK refers to the knowledge that teachers develop about how to teach particular content/subject matter in ways that lead to enhanced student understanding of that content (Laughran et al. (2012)). It acknowledges that educators must have both (i) an acute understanding of their subject matter, and (ii) a deep knowledge of teaching and pedagogy, to develop an effective learning environment and course for students. Without PCK, a well-informed expert or scholar may be unable to make their knowledge understandable or accessible to learners, thus it is an imperative element in the knowledge transfer process. In turn, those with effective pedagogical content knowledge will be able to use a number of pedagogical tools and approaches to enthuse learners about topics, and engage them in active and transformative lessons. As an extension, Koehler et al. (2014) introduce the TPACK model to integrate the theme of technical knowledge, noting its importance when developing courses which have technical learning/skill development. This model

also refers to teacher knowledge about traditional and new technologies that can be integrated into curriculum.

Figure 3: TPACK Framework (Koehler et al., 2014. P. 9)

When embarking on the development of a new way of exploring and teaching a topic, particularly one which is intended to be mixed-modality (online, offline, workshop), and cross-disciplinary, it is imperative that multiple considerations of pedagogy be considered. In this section, we will explore the student as a hybrid learner and the use of MOOC's and online technology. In addition, the BC4ECO project aims to change student mindset about sustainability and develop key critical thinking skills, we will explore potential impediments to this, in the form of cognitive biases. Finally, we will focus on the concepts of Ecopedagogies, highlighting the significance of tackling environmental sustainability with a critical and systemic outlook, as well as the notion of Decentralisation, deemed

essential to facilitate a distributed mindset in the context of collaborative group work and complex challenges.

2.2.1 Online Learning and the Hybrid Student

Universities are now highly attended and deeply internationalised institutions, and can face challenges in teaching large classes (Maringe & Sing, 2014; Saunders and Hutt, 2015). Reasons for this growing trend are multiple and complex; including marketization, student mobility increases and stagnation in staff hiring strategies (Maringe & Sing, 2014). Coupled with financial constraints, educators are often forced into economy of scale type teaching models, with larger class contexts and more automated assessment (Trees & Jackson, 2007). All of these factors combine to spur even more focus on the use of online learning, and more novel approaches to hybrid curriculum delivery - using a mix of online and offline methodologies.

Online learning refers to instruction delivered electronically through various multimedia and Internet platforms and applications. It is used interchangeably with other terms such as web-based learning, e-learning, computer-assisted instruction, and Internet-based learning. As our use of technology becomes more complex, the array of tools and methods to deliver online learning grows and adapts. Massive Open Online Courses or MOOCs have grown exponentially as a mechanism to engage distance learners, short-course learners and to develop content that can be scaled as offerings for multiple cohorts (Kizilcec, Pérez-Sanagustín, & Maldonado, 2017). Kizilcec et al. (2017) investigated self-regulated learning in a sample of 4,831 learners across six MOOCs finding that goal setting and strategic planning predicted attainment of personal course goals.

When looking at the target group for this learning framework, it is relevant to understand how complex problems cannot be fully understood or solved through the lens of a single discipline. Undoubtedly, the use of technology and the technical aspects necessary to work with it, require the development of competencies that enable learners to effectively implement technical solutions within a specific context. Nevertheless, technological implications and the way we perceive technology in a post-modern society require much more than this. In Benjamin Bratton's 'the Stack' (2015), there is an underlying assumption that the technological development that our world inherited throughout history, is an 'accidental megastructure' that recursively influences the way we shape it as well as the way in which we are automatically shaped by it. A key aspect of Bratton's work is the fact that such 'Stack' is not only a collection of technologies, but also a set of social, political, and economic systems that are intertwined and interdependent within technological discourses (ibid.). If we think of DLTs as components of such a Stack, where decentralised and disruptive technology influence and challenge the principle of governance and democracy, then – as Bratton suggests – designing for such a 'Stack' requires a multidisciplinary approach that takes into account critical and non-technical methods to design and develop it. This type of approach is holistic and requires not only the technical aspects for development but also a broader approach to handle and reflect upon technological implications. Such an

assumption makes it clear how innovating within DLTs implies a multidisciplinary approach where many fields intersect.

To deal with the current need for flexible learning trajectories giving access to a more diverse group of learners, synchronous hybrid virtual classrooms have been designed to connect both on-site students and remote students during synchronous teaching. A study by Raes et al. (2020) compared students' learning experiences as F2F versus virtual, in the pure or hybrid setting. The results show that although the hybrid virtual classroom is promising regarding learner flexibility of location, it is also the most challenging one to teach in and to learn in as a remote participant. It has been found that both the relatedness to peers and the intrinsic motivation is the lowest in the hybrid-virtual setting.

For online learning and MOOCs, completion rates for online courses are usually significantly lower than for courses where instruction occurs face-to-face (Dietz-Uhler, Fisher & Han, 2007). As such, hybrid experiences which utilise online content in effective manners but retain engaging live in-class and experiential events may be the optimum approach. Developing optimum pedagogical frameworks, and committing time to the creation and testing of both the curriculum and the teaching tools/technique is critical to the success of impactful hybrid learning. For example, when choosing pedagogical tools to use when engaging the hybrid students, Raes et al. (2020) found that quizzes were positively related to student motivation. In turn, different students will engage with the materials in discrete ways, for example learners with stronger self-regulated skills were more likely to revisit previously studied course materials, especially course assessments (Kizilcec et al., 2017).

2.2.2 Behavioural Change and Critical Thinking

Cognitive biases and heuristics are important in developing a novel pedagogical framework in which students utilise DLTs for Environmental Sustainability because they can affect how students perceive and respond to environmental issues and how they make decisions related to technology and sustainability. Understanding these biases and heuristics can help educators design pedagogies that address them, to help students make more informed and rational decisions about designing patterns for sustainable behaviours (Lockton et al., 2015).

Cognitive biases are systematic patterns of deviation from norm or rationality in judgment, whereby inferences about other people, objects, or situations may be drawn in an illogical fashion (Kahneman, 2013). These biases are often a result of the brain's attempt to simplify information processing. Researchers are divided on whether cognitive biases should be seen as errors or as rational shortcuts (Gigerenzer, 2011). Some suggest they should be referred to as "behavioural tendencies" rather than "cognitive biases" (Kahneman, 2013). They have been extensively studied in the field of behavioural science and decision-making (Acciarini et al., 2020). Some common examples include:

- The egocentric empathy gap, documented by Van Boven et al. (2000), which causes decision-makers to project the value of their own preferences over the value of others.
- The illusion of control (Lietdka, 2015), also known as the ‘planning fallacy’ describes how individuals might overestimate the success of a made decision.
- The availability bias (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974), make us project past events as something that would most likely occur in the future.
- The representativeness bias (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974), in which we tend to assume that what we see or experience is representative of all possibilities, also taking into account our limited exposure to alternative options when making decisions.
- The confirmation bias (Snyder & Swann, 1978), influences the process of interpreting new information to confirm our initial assumptions rather than criticising them.
- The status quo bias (Samuelson & Zeckhauser, 1988), which leads us to decisions that are geared towards maintaining an already existing state of things.
- And *the loss aversion bias* (Kahneman et al., 1991) which implies how eliminating the risk of losing, is better than increasing the odds of winning.

Cognitive biases play an important role in how people think about and respond to climate change (Holmgren et al., 2019), for example, by being more likely to believe in climate change on hot days, or by being more likely to dismiss it as a threat when its effects are perceived as far away from one's immediate experience. Cognitive biases also explain why, despite the overwhelming scientific evidence, a significant portion of people remains sceptical about climate change. Some of the biases highlighted in sustainability research include the compensatory green beliefs (Kaklamanou et al., 2015), the negative footprint illusion (Gorissen & Weijters, 2016) and the limitations of long-term thinking (King, 2019).

It is important to consider not only the impact of technology and personal biases on environmental sustainability but also ways to avoid being influenced by our own assumptions and mental shortcuts when making decisions. Critical thinking may play a key role in helping individuals overcome cognitive biases by providing a systematic and reflective approach to evaluating information and making decisions, (Battersby & Bailin, 2013); Godhe & Godhe, 2018). Students engaged with critical thinking challenge their cognitive assumptions by dissecting, analysing, interpreting, connecting and ideating over specific challenges (Aufa et al., 2021). Therefore, pedagogies whose underpinnings are centred on critical thinking, encourage students to respond to social, economic and environmental issues and positively uncover the potential for preferable futures (Minott et al., 2019). As we are discussing the intersection between technical and non-technical roles of learners to address complex challenges, then as Minott et al. (2019) suggest “a pedagogical dialogue is needed in which strengths and weaknesses in the

views of all stakeholders are utilised as assets for sustainable development for the present and the future”.

2.2.3 Ecopedagogies - addressing sustainability education

Given the focus on sustainability that permeates our mission and the subject being taught, we must consider the sustainability context within our pedagogical framework. The BC4ECO project provides an opportunity to engage in a multidisciplinary, problem-based, and decentralised pedagogical framework that presents a stimulating platform to analyse real-life environmental challenges through the prisms of critical and design thinking. It emphasises the notion that technology should not be viewed as a mere means to an end, but as an instrument to investigate and assess the social impact of design choices. For this reason we find it relevant to embrace the analysis and contribution from ecopedagogical discourses and integrate them in this pedagogical framework.

Ecopedagogy refers to a field of study that aims to explore and address the complex intersection between education and the environment. Kahn (2010) considers it important to address climate challenges by distancing oneself from the notion of sustainable development as it has been advocated by market-driven, technocratic and functionalistic discourses (Misziasek, 2020), proposing instead an approach to sustainability that combats environmental injustices and favours the politics of socio-environmental awareness (Kahn, 2010; Misziasek, 2020). Ecopedagogy has been defined by many as a movement between critical dialogue and complexity (Norat et al., 2016), where the learnings emerging from Freire’s critical pedagogy (1997) invites the dismantling of anthropocentric narratives that fueled the matrix of domination, i.e. as the ones concerning the relationship human-nature (Collins, 1993), to welcome approaches to ecoliteracy that adopts economic, social, technological concepts (Kahn, 2010). In operationalising these ecopedagogical principles into the curriculum, Hadjichambis et al. (2020) demonstrate that environmental awareness requires a mix of learning foundations that are inquiry-based – or Problem-Based, and critical to the extent that learners can create their own understanding of the world and challenge at the same time their own belief systems (Hui & Seow, 2022). Problem-Based Learning and critical thinking are core pillars for BC4ECO’s learning pedagogy and resonate with what Marouli (2021) stressed as the importance of empowering learners in becoming constructive philosopher-agents of change that envision, design and build a more sustainable future.

Integrating multiple perspectives in the process of problematisation of environmental challenges is considered to redefine the learner’s concept of ‘development’ and embraces the study of systems and democratic engagement to understand how to better address sustainable solutions. The UNESCO Education for sustainable development program (ESD) (UNESCO, 2014) recommends the promotion of skills that deal with and understand complex systems, conceptualising future scenarios, and favouring decision-making through participatory and collaborative ways (Hjorth Warlenius, 2022).

Considering other necessary modes of thinking valuable to the teaching of sustainability topics, Wang et al. (2022) note that systematic thinking orientation, transformative orientation, co-creation

orientation, and sustainability orientation are important facets of social innovation education and are much needed to solve multi-layered and complex social problems. Adopting reflexive approaches, and the ability to critically analyse one's own experiences and assumptions in relation to the world (Misiaszek et al., 2022) could empower learners in adopting the necessary mindset to understand causes and consequences of complex challenges. Systems thinking in this case, enables learners to see how individual components work together to create larger patterns or systems, which often lead them to new insights about wicked problems being addressed (Dentoni et. al, 2020).

2.2.4 Decentralisation

When examining the learning pedagogy and its objectives, it is important to consider the notion of decentralisation within the context of DLTs. Decentralisation is a key aspect of DLTs and has the potential to influence the way in which the technology impacts society. Within BC4ECO, the multidisciplinary perspective on decentralisation not only refers to the need to understand the functioning of decentralised systems (creating autonomy, reducing power asymmetries, creating trust) but such a concept adds value to the overall pedagogy focusing on the methodology required to design decentralised innovation. Thus, it is crucial to understand the implications of decentralisation in order to fully grasp the potential of DLTs and their effect on the learning pedagogy.

Decentralised systems/networks are far more resilient and adaptive than centralised ones and independent from any central governance (Bodó et al., 2021). Building a decentralised mindset means approaching problems where multiple perspectives, approaches, and solutions are possible, and where groups of individuals value diversity, inclusivity, collaboration, and autonomy while seeking to find solutions that are decentralized, distributed, and adaptable (Sims, 2019). If decentralised systems are more resilient and adaptive than centralised ones, then a *decentralised mindset* is necessary for building and maintaining such systems. Especially when applied within sustainable endeavours, it requires a shift of paradigm for students and designers, too used to thinking in a centralised or self-centred way. With a learning pedagogy, BC4ECO aims at challenging a centralised way of thinking, to encourage innovative practices for learning. Relevant inspiration from decentralised thinking has also been highlighted by Kahn (2010), following Deleuze and Guattari's concept of the 'rhizome', described as a decentralised, non-hierarchical way of thinking about knowledge and the world (Marenko & Brassat, 2015). The rhizome is a metaphor for a type of network where ideas or knowledge are interconnected and conceptualisation should not be attached to any central point of authority. Ivan Illich's concept of the 'learning web' (Illich, 1972) shares many similarities with the rhizome analogy and Illich strongly rejects centralised learning in favour of decentralised ways of thinking and learning. The plethora of media technologies available to learners nowadays should be exploited as a way to encourage the adoption of several sources of information presenting many forms and developed throughout distributed access points (f.e. Social Media platforms). This pedagogical framework utilizes these concepts and tries to replicate a decentralised way of designing. This can be applied by using various digital tools to access and share knowledge, collaborating in team-work settings to explore complex problems, and engaging

in democratic decision-making processes to shape the direction of preferable solutions to enhance the learning experience.

3. The BC4ECO pedagogical framework

3.1 Vision

Throughout the presentation of this concept paper, it has become evident that the pressing issue of environmental sustainability necessitates the development of novel pedagogical frameworks that incorporate technological innovation and a systemic understanding of the impact of such technology on societies and cultures worldwide. The wickedness of compound problems that affect the environment and our societies call for novel capabilities and novel approaches to teaching and learning. This should be understood as a key shift of paradigm in which processes for change go in parallel with a shift in perspective on how to tackle and discuss certain issues. For this reason, one key aspect taken into account through the frames of this pedagogy is the behavioural one, which draws environmental and technological awareness into play, as a way to innovate within the domain of environmental sustainability. In fact, when outlining the vision of the learning model itself, **the BC4ECO pedagogy aims at inspiring and supporting learners to succeed as creative, critical and environmentally conscious thinkers.**

3.2 Learning goals

The underpinnings for this learning pedagogy are to promote learning pathways to motivate learners in embracing decentralised and critical thinking and raise awareness about environmental issues. Through problem and design-based learning the pedagogy also aims to mitigate students' preconceived assumptions and cognitive biases when dealing with complex sustainability challenges. The looming environmental crisis calls for a shift of focus towards a world-centred education which scholars argue is needed now more than ever (Biesta, 2022). As a result, a shift of focus brings along many other pedagogical attempts to dismantle traditional structures of teaching and learning, which do not necessarily reshape institutions but rather encourage pedagogues and learners to adopt more critical and problem-based capabilities. The wicked and multifaceted nature of environmental challenges requires a creative and decentralised approach, which through distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) and design thinking might stimulate novel ways to formulate problems and develop solutions. Due to the iterative nature of design methodologies, these approaches are appropriate when studying wicked problems, that do not have specific criteria for success, but rather take problem formulation as a key driver for learning and innovating.

In this pedagogical framework, learners will:

- Acquire background knowledge through a networked learning environment to better navigate the context of challenges and opportunities for DLTs (lectures, online material and OERs, P2P, case studies).
- Reflect on real-case studies to understand – within group work settings – how DLTs technologies are applied within Environmental Sustainability. In this way, learners will develop those necessary critical skills that will mitigate potential biases and assumptions.
- Develop their own design process, where different design capabilities facilitate critical thinking to address problem formulation for systemic challenges.
- Acquire a decentralised mindset while improving their environmental awareness within a bounded timeframe.

3.3 Target Audience/Learner Profile

Identifying the target group of the BC4ECO’s novel learning pedagogy a multidisciplinary approach is taken by considering a diverse range of students that can benefit our novel pedagogy (Table 10). Yet, given the technological nature of the concepts inherent within blockchain technology, it is understood that a base understanding of computing or engineering, or design is required. In order to allow our target audience to benefit fully from the course, we intend to relay the content in a stepwise manner, revising some introductory and key foundational concepts at the outset, then moving to more complex applications of “Blockchain for Sustainability” topics.

Primary Target Group	<u>Master and Doctoral students & educators within the field of:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer Science / ICT • Design • Environmental Sustainability / Engineering
Secondary Target Group	<u>Adult Learners (outside HEI) and</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer Science / ICT • Design • Environmental Sustainability / Engineering

Table 10: Primary and Secondary target group for the Pedagogical Framework

BC4ECO initially seeks to engage with learners in two ways:

1. Institutional-level students enrolled in the Summer Schools connected to the BC4ECO project and participating universities through officially released courses.
2. Universities and colleges that seek to strengthen and standardise their educational offerings in the fields of DLTs and Environmental Sustainability. These institutions would leverage the content and BC4ECO offerings for their own courses - externally to the deliverables of the BC4ECO project.

3.4 Teaching Philosophy

Overall, the pedagogical framework is built using a constructivist Problem-Based Learning (PBL) lens, where design processes thrive and favours the development of critical thinking and environmental awareness. In a constructivist approach, such as in the case of Problem-Based Learning, the principles for teaching and learning are centred around the idea that learners construct their own understanding of the world through meaningful engagement with relevant experiences. As already described in Section 2.1, PBL thrives in environments which leverage a student-centred learning approach to real-life challenges. Such challenges - or cases, will enable learners to critically evaluate the relationships between different actors of an ecosystem by using DLTs to address sustainable innovation. This process of design through active inquiry encourages learning through an ongoing and iterative circle of feedback, happening at different stages and within a collaborative setting. The application of critical thinking exercises into a design-based learning pedagogy, will increase environmental awareness and mitigate the potential biases encountered while working with systemic challenges. In addition, the consideration to the decentralised and non-functional features of DLTs, this pedagogy aims at promoting a decentralised mindset in both teaching and learning activities in a way to empower designers to think and design for decentralised systems.

3.5 Principles for teaching and learning

Before highlighting the different approaches that inform the design and implementation of teaching practices, it is important to consider the key principles that inform and underpin our pedagogical decisions. These are:

Decentralisation as core

Decentralisation is a key aspect of DLTs and has the potential to influence the way in which the technology impacts society. Building a decentralised mindset means approaching problems where multiple perspectives are incorporated, and power or decision-making is spread across stakeholders rather than localised within a hierarchical structure. BC4ECO will aim to incorporate the tenants of decentralisation in its design, pedagogy and communication with students in a number of ways, from the way resources are structured and accessed by the learners as well as from the methodological approach required to tackle sustainable innovation and DLTs.

Embracing multiple thinking modes: Critical, Design and Systems

Core to the creation of the BC4ECO framework is an acknowledgement that learners will need multiple and divergent thinking modes to assess information and solve problems. As such we focus on the development of critical, design and systems thinking skills.

- Critical Thinking is a necessary teaching practice that challenges traditional ways of thinking and instantiates available pathways for preferable futures. Students will be encouraged to think critically and creatively in order to identify and analyse a problem, generate possible solutions, and evaluate and choose the best course of action to develop decentralised innovation towards Environmental Sustainability.
- Design thinking can help students to connect and empathize with respective social groups, to identify and solve problems creatively
- Systems thinking can help students understand how different elements of a system interact with each other. System thinking, particularly mapping systems, when paired with design thinking offers a powerful combination for addressing wicked societal problems with innovative solutions.

Design-based collaboration

Collaborating in groups will enhance students' self-directed learning and empower them to take responsibility for the knowledge they generate. In this way, the approach taken by the learners towards different case studies will be facilitated by various exercises expressed throughout events and courses, to help learners collaboratively test out solutions and iteratively support their problem formulation. It is hoped that this collaboration will involve multiple stakeholders and voices from a host of multidisciplinary backgrounds.

Accessible and Networked knowledge

The promotion of learning material through OERs, will help learners in becoming independent from frontal lectures, and – also in this way, promote self-directed learning. The role of MOOCs, case studies, online resources and collaborative platforms for learning is key to providing multiple sources of information that can support the creation of potential solutions in a way that is diverse, decentralised and free from temporal constraints. It is hoped that this accessibility to learning will inspire learners to be proactive in their search for knowledge, enhancing their potential as lifelong learners.

Authentic Learning Experiences

As a core element of problem and design-based learning, engaging learners in rich experiential learning using real-life cases and applied projects is critical to transformative change and development.

3.6 Key teaching practices

When discussing teaching practices, we refer to those strategies and methods that are used within BC4ECO to implement teaching theories within a classroom setting. Below we list different teaching practices that serve as key strategic activities to inform the learning pedagogy in different contexts, both online as well as in a physical setup. Informed by the teaching principles outlined in Section 3.3, we have chosen to include a number of specific teaching practices which will permeate our delivery of BC4ECO. These are:

Open-ended & critical problem formulations

Through open-ended & critical problem formulations, learners will not focus on finding definitive answers, as knowledge creation applied to entangled problems, favours a more explorative rather than normative approach to problem-solving. The development of non-linear and non-task-oriented learning will help students to accommodate and embrace uncertainty allowing them to engage with the complex nature of their solutions. The design process embraces this uncertainty, and within a PBL setting, it will be possible to invite learners in challenging their predisposed biases and assumptions in order to favour more conscious reasoning in the analysis of a specific context.

Unbounded information

Teachers will develop syllabus content to cover the key technical aspects of DLTs and Environmental Challenges and provide the students with a solid foundation on how to prototype potential solutions. Such knowledge will not be limited to explicit course content but also include valuable case studies and documentation that will be later displayed throughout the different digital platforms and made available to learners. Learners will be provided with resources and access to platforms which they can engage in extended and self-directed learning about related topics.

Flipped classroom

Teachers will set up specific platforms/ environments that facilitate the group work setup as well as the P2P knowledge exchange. (e.g. Slack, Teams, Miro). The role of the teacher will become secondary, as the students will become self-learners within real-life challenges. The platforms will not only serve as a space for online collaboration and communication, but they will be used to keep track of research artefacts, make sense of data collection as well as ideate and test possible solutions.

Real-life case studies

Problem-based learning is a method that uses real-world problems as a way to teach students concepts and principles. Instead of just teaching facts and concepts, students learn by working on actual problems. They will be used as vehicles for learning and will encourage the adoption of critical skills to generate innovative ways to address – and work with complexity. Guest speakers, site visits (online/offline) and other methodologies will also be integrated to provide learners with grounded experiences.

Design tools and processes

Teachers will give students various tools to examine ecosystems and networks where values are exchanged among *humans, technology, and the environment*. The use of digital platforms for collaboration (such as Miro) or design tools such as stakeholder mapping, Business Model Canvas, value ecosystem mapping, as well as many canvases to collaboratively work with decentralised technologies will be incorporated into the course design. These will also help students understand how to articulate and put into practice problem formulations and reflection on interconnected values. When working with open-ended problem formulations, learners will be encouraged to critically reflect and understand the value of individual autonomy and agency in a distributed ledger technology (DLT) for sustainability.

Scoping Exercises - multiple source methodologies

The review of multiple sources of information will grant the students the opportunity to evaluate different types of sources by critically reflecting on their origins. Such types of sources work as different types of signals that will help the students to identify ideas and insights on the matter of inquiry. This comprises case studies, technologies, interviews with experts, articles, publications etc.

3.7 Pedagogical evaluation

Given the need to address the development of critical thinking, and design skills as well as the promotion of a decentralised, environmentally conscious mindset, it is essential that the evaluation criteria do not rely solely on traditional methods and tools. In order to effectively assess the progress and effectiveness of the BC4ECO project there is the need to assess and capture nuances of learning that might result in difficulty to grasp under traditional methods. Evaluating critical learning within a pedagogical framework is similar to evaluating general learning, but it may involve using different assessment techniques that are better suited to measuring critical thinking skills. Some examples of assessment techniques that can be used to evaluate critical learning include open-ended questions, case studies, and the presentation of output material by the end of a specific event or course. These types of assessments often require students to apply their knowledge and critical thinking skills to real-world situations, which can provide a more accurate measure of their understanding of the material. In addition to using these types of assessments, it can also be helpful to provide students with regular feedback on their process and to give them opportunities to reflect on their learning and identify areas for

improvement. When considering an evaluation of design-based learning, Gomez et al. (2012) highlight a number of effective methods. A selection of these will be utilised by the BC4ECO team to capture the experiences of the learners and staff members.

Assessment	Examples
Formative	Individual and group tasks Weekly online quizzes; laboratory work Weekly presentations; reports; prototype; concept design Intermediate checkpoints based on intermediate deliverables: improvements in reports; prototypes; quality of experiments
Summative	Individual contribution to project group; oral exams; final exam Presentations; reports Portfolio assessment; peer- and self-assessment Use of rubrics Involvement of industry representatives in assessment

Table 11: Characteristics of DBL pertaining to assessment (Gomez Puente et al., 2012)

Additional evaluation measures

Due to the hybrid nature of our intended delivery, there are more opportunities to evaluate its performance and value to the learner.

BC4ECO as an event:

In considering the learning courses (e.g. intense short courses or summer schools) as events, we can capture a range of useful evaluative information. In particular, this data for evaluation refer to the assessment of learning within the context of where the Pedagogical Framework will be applied in BC4ECO:

- Participant numbers and demographics.
- Participant engagement during the event/course.
- Participant identified level of interest;
- Number of participants who completed the activity;

- Participant learning from the event/course.
- Comparison of pre-and post-event knowledge of the topic;
- Quality of questions and discussions;
- Evidence of advanced thinking in learning tasks
- Innovative value of the project outputs
- Participant suggestions for improvement and general feedback
- Design output/material created during the event

BC4ECO as online learning:

Through the online activities and MOOC based content it may be possible to collect information about user engagement, duration of engagement, proficiency via online quizzes, and knowledge or discourse via online forums and posts.

BC4ECO as research:

The use of qualitative, quantitative and experimental methods (delphi etc.) may be also used to attain a nuanced understanding of the learner and their journey in the module. This would be especially to gain an insight into the transformative effect of the courses on learner intentions for sustainable change and impact.

4. How this framework will be used within BC4ECO and beyond

The pedagogical framework, being a set of principles and practices on teaching and learning, will be used as a frame of reference to guide the other projects' results. The idea is that this pedagogical framework can be used to ensure that the content developed throughout the project is aligned with the learning objectives, that each delivery method is appropriate for the target audience and that the evaluation of the pedagogy from both students and external stakeholders can be used to inform the completion of the other projects' results.

Result	How will the pedagogical framework inform this result?
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<p>R2: Curriculum Design of the Course "Blockchain for the Environment"</p>	<p>The curriculum will be developed based on the pedagogical framework, which will guide the structure of the course "Blockchain for the Environment" together with the teaching and learning practices used. The course will take place in 2 different Summer School events as well as a Teacher Training Workshop as part of R6.</p>
<p>R3: MOOC 1: Basis of Blockchain for the Environment</p>	<p>When looking at the role of decentralised learning the pedagogical framework stresses the importance of MOOCs as a way to distribute the pedagogies' principles for teaching and learning into OERs.</p>
<p>R4: MOOC 2: Leverage Blockchain for the Environment</p>	<p>Following the same criteria for the first MOOC (R3), the second MOOC is built as a continuation of the first one and follows the same principles described in the learning pedagogy. In this case, the learning principles will be much more focused on both technical and non-technical aspects of the pedagogy, involving DLTs, Environmental Sustainability, critical thinking and design-based learning.</p>
<p>R5: Ecosystem for learning and project development</p>	<p>The Ecosystem for learning and project development ensures that the learning pedagogy will be linked to wider communities of DLT experts, environmental activists and designers.</p>
<p>R6: Teacher Guide</p>	<p>The Pedagogical Framework will inform the organisation of a Teacher Training Workshop</p>

Table 12: How the learning pedagogy informs each of the BC4ECO's project results

Following the principles of distributed learning, different OERs will be used to disseminate the philosophical underpinnings as well as practices for teaching and learning. The different project results emerging from the framework will be distributed through the project website and Zenodo platform; besides being adapted into MOOCs they will also be presented through different events, seen as venues for dissemination. The twofold nature of the target group invites this framework to become available for various other stakeholders that can benefit from the various items of the learning pedagogy. Schools, private institutions and overall communities will be engaged throughout multiple events as well as open communities that will contribute to the sustainability purposes of the project.

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